

THEORETICAL FUNDAMENTALS OF DEVELOPMENT OF FARM ACTIVITIES

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ABSTRACT

Theoretical aspects of the theoretical basis of the development of farming are described. The search for and introduction of new approaches, models and methods for the development of farming is described in detail. Factors influencing the development of farming have been studied.

A dehkan farm is a small family farm that grows and sells agricultural products on a plot of land that is inherited and given to the head of the family for lifelong possession, based on the personal labor of family members.

Dehkan farms cannot use paid labor on a permanent basis.

PF of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 9, 2017 "On measures to radically improve the system of protection of the rights and legitimate interests of farmers, dehkan farms and landowners, the efficient use of agricultural land" Decree No. 5199 of October 10, 2017 "On organizational measures for further development of the activities of farmers, dehkan farms and landowners" in order to

carry out the tasks set out in Resolution PQ-3318, the following cases were studied.

The author of the works "Farming", "Organization of farms" A.V.Chayanov, taking into account the personal interests and labor of the farmer, said that the task of the farm - to find the means of subsistence through the use of drugs", described. It is noteworthy that the scientific work of A.V.Chayanov was directly aimed at the organization and efficiency of farming. In his work, the theoretical aspects of the formation and development of farms as a business entity have been developed as a result of long research and studies, but there are also contradictory opinions based on them.

Another Russian economist, D.F. Vermel, said that in developing agriculture, first of all:

distribution of the land plot according to certain dimensions in the organization of the farm;

in particular, the establishment of small enterprises processing agricultural products on a farm basis to provide the population with food, equipping them with advanced technology and equipment of leading foreign companies;

In the end, it was noted that the organization of production of quality, competitive, export-oriented domestic products is a priority.

Another important reason for the emphasis on the development of farms is that the effective operation of these entities depends on their sustainable operation without the need for large investments. The creation of a free competitive environment in the context of market relations will ensure the development of this area rather than leading to more crises. As a result, farms are virtually free of crises and are able to adapt quickly to market fluctuations.

Therefore, we believe that encouraging farmers to become more efficient will have the following positive effects:

- the involvement of the surplus of the able-bodied population, especially women and young people living in rural areas, in socially useful work, and thus the risk of rising unemployment elimination is achieved;

- increase of real incomes of the population, and also strengthening of social guarantees for the rural population;

- Eliminate tensions in the provision of vital food products to the population.

Families who receive plots of land not only meet their needs for potatoes, vegetables, fruits, and livestock products, but also increase their share in solving the food problem by significantly increasing their sales in district centers or urban farmers' markets;

- Significantly expand the scale of individual housing construction, which will help to solve many problems in the field of housing, improvement of communal (housing) and housing conditions of the population of the republic;

- not only to eliminate the causes and sources of social conflicts, but also to take an active part in the improvement of people's private lands and gardens, courtyards.

It is advisable to use it to improve the activities of farms of the country, including:

- Ensuring that farmers enter into contracts with the state for the purchase of certain agricultural products and that some products are purchased by the state at high prices (German, Israeli experience);

- government incentives for low-profit agricultural producers (milk, meat) to support the domestic market (German experience);

- Economic incentives for farms that use agricultural land efficiently, improve its reclamation status, and organize production based on the use of alternative energy sources (Germany, USA, Israel experience);

- Preservation of the country's traditions of production based on agricultural specialization (German, Israeli experience);

- Improving cooperative relations based on the principles of mass cooperation and allowing farms to operate

as members of several associations and cooperatives (German and Israeli experience);

- Availability of state quotas for dairy products, meat products, eggs and potatoes, which are the most important food products (German, US experience);

- The right to obtain a patent for farms engaged in the provision of agricultural products, rather than their cultivation (Russian experience);

- The existence of traditional efforts to educate qualified farmers in the future, including the organization of master classes, thematic clubs, experimental fields on the basis of various agricultural associations (EU, US experience);

- Development of the Leader Program Methodology to increase the competitiveness of agricultural products, improve the environment and rural conditions, the quality of life in rural areas and diversify agriculture (EU experience);

- Operation of the Economic Research Service (ERS) in the Ministry of Agriculture to promote and improve the activities of family farms as the main subjects of cooperation in the agro-food complex (US experience);

- A clear statement of the activities and responsibilities of the Ministry of Agriculture:

- plant and animal health and disease control in the country;

- prevention of overproduction in the country and assistance in stabilizing prices (Israeli experience).

Dehkan farm has the following rights as a business entity:

- independent organization of production activities of the farm on the allotted land plot;

- independent pricing of products grown and sold;

- exercise the right to sell its products, including those sold to consumers at will;

- conclusion of prepaid futures contracts for the purchased product;

- to receive an unlimited amount of profit from entrepreneurship;

- purchase of shares for sale to agricultural producers and free trade;

- pledge their property, as well as the right of lifelong inheritance of the land plot, including the right acquired at auction.

Dehkan farms established as a legal entity may receive loans for the implementation of their activities, property and funds of other legal entities and individuals on a voluntary basis and on a contractual basis, including the necessary collateral for repayment of loans to dehkan farms. can be involved in preferential lending with medium and other guarantees, as well as enjoy all types of benefits provided for private small business.

The construction of facilities of agricultural importance for production, long-term lending for the purchase of fixed assets and short-term lending for current production activities are carried out on the basis of a loan agreement.

In the agricultural sector, agricultural products produced by private entities play an effective role in the development of our economy. This is reflected in the following: - The development of small business and private entrepreneurship in the agricultural sector has not only provided for the peasant family, but also turned farmers into commercial farms and acquired the skills

to grow products for the market. As a result, the consumer market of the republic is full of cheap and high-quality food products; - The issue of food security of the population at the expense of small-scale production and private property, which are flexible to the conditions of a market economy, has become a major source of social stability in society. served. This is evidenced by the fact that today 60-70% of food products and 90% of certain types are grown by farmers; - The development of peasants and farms has stimulated the development of market infrastructure in rural areas; - The development of farmers and farms has made it possible to increase the production of competitive, high-quality agricultural products and export them. However, despite the measures taken and the positive results achieved, a number of problems hinder the further development of these businesses.

Including:

- The economic, legal and technological knowledge of many existing farmers and farm managers is not at the required level, so it is advisable to organize regular training seminars for farmers;

- There are difficulties in selling vegetables, fruits and other products grown on farms. To this end, it is necessary, first of all, to create favorable conditions for farmers to sell their products by conducting marketing research, allocating special places in farmers' markets and establishing wholesale purchasing organizations;

- Dehkan farms, like other types of agricultural enterprises, are an equal form of management, and the mechanism for organizing farms and encouraging them should be reconsidered and improved;

- Provision of information and consulting services to small businesses and private entrepreneurs engaged in agricultural production in rural areas is not organized at the required level. Due to the limited technical capabilities of the established information and consulting centers, the range of services provided by the link is limited, as well as they are not provided with qualified personnel. Most farmers do not know how to use the services of such a center.

Farmers have been able to use their land more efficiently, implement agro-technical measures, introduce fast-ripening and high-yielding varieties, and achieve better yields as a result of better labor organization. Observations have shown that in recent years, cereals, vegetables, fruits, grapes and potatoes have been recognized as the main crops in the distribution of arable land in the province's farms. The Presidential Decree of January 9, 2006 "On measures to deepen economic reforms in the fruit and vegetable and viticulture sectors" served as a guideline. This is due to the fact that the area allocated for gardens and vineyards has increased by 26-28% compared to 2000.

Using the analyzed economic results to create an econometric model of increasing the volume of production in the activities of farms, taking into account the nature of the growth rate of gross agricultural output and the specifics of the agricultural sector The volume of gross agricultural output (billion soums) - $Y(t)$, which is the end result (outcome indicator), was selected. The dependent variables that affect the resultant character, that is, to increase the production of important agricultural products: gross agricultural output, gross

livestock production, the population employed on farms, the area of arable land attached to farms, etc. factors were selected.

The purpose of running a farm is to create a commodity for domestic consumption and commodity production, as well as to ensure the material well-being of oneself and one's family through other activities. The main task of the peasantry is to achieve the rational use of production resources by involving the rural population in productive labor and entrepreneurship, and on this basis to increase production at the lowest cost. Dehkan farms also contribute to the solution of a number of tasks, such as the efficient use of land resources, contributing to the food needs of the population, participation in the social development of the region in which it is located.

Farming as one of the forms of entrepreneurship in the agricultural sector has a number of advantages: - The small volume of production allows you to quickly adapt to market conditions and reshape their activities without spending a lot of money; - Reliance on family labor creates conditions for the effective use of the experience of housewives and children, the elderly, as well as the transmission of centuries-old agricultural culture from generation to generation; - Private ownership and the transfer of land for lifetime with the right of inheritance

increases the material interest and allows the rational use of property.

In short, there are districts in the region that have the largest number of farms and the largest share. Of these, 49,815 in Chirakchi (14% of the total number), 43,832 in Kasan district (12.3%), 43,808 in Karshi (12.1%), 39,935 in Yakkabog (11.7%), 38,200 in Kamashi district. (11%) and 30,000 (10.2%) farms in Karshi district and 20,200 (9.8%) farms in Nishan district, which are important and integral parts of the regional economy. . This means that "if the production of all types of farms is raised to the level of efficient farms, there is an opportunity to increase the amount of food produced by 1.8-2.0 times."

The emergence of farms as a new form of management in the agricultural sector, on the one hand, allows the emergence of real ownership, on the other hand, creates a certain competitive environment with enterprises based on other forms of ownership. Entrepreneurial activities are those related to domestic production and the production of small-scale agricultural products and based on the individual labor of farm members. Farms independently determine the direction of their activities, the structure and volume of production. The measures taken in our country to develop farms are yielding positive results.

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